

TO THE AUSTRALIAN MARINE SCIENCES ASSOCIATION
SYMPOSIUM ON POLLUTION IN THE MARINE ENVIRONMENT
AUGUST 1970

STATEMENT OF DISENCHANTMENT

The signatories of this statement question the motives behind AMSA's symposium on pollution.

Public concern for the environment may be new; the ecocide that gave rise to it is not. The marine environment has been deteriorating for a long time and marine scientists were in a position years ago to inform the public that the crisis was approaching. We believe, therefore, that this symposium should have been held at least ten years ago. But it wasn't and there seem to be four possible reasons:

either, marine scientists were scientifically incompetent and did not see what was happening;
or, they were so brainwashed by a culture dedicated to economic growth that they could not see or refused to see;
or, they were scientifically immoral because they saw but being personally untouched did not care to speak out;
or, their vested interests were such that they preferred personal gain and career advancement to speaking out.

It is other people, notably amateur groups, that have brought the issue to the public eye. Senior scientists have not been to the fore in this campaign. Does the scientific community speak out now simply to recoup its lost prestige and authority? Have the issues that concern us here simply been siezed upon as a counter-weapon to the molecular scientists "cancer research", and does this symposium, therefore, end up just so much good public relations in the fight for funds?

If this symposium lends support, either consciously or unconsciously to the view that "progress" equals "economic growth" or if it aligns itself in any way with those institutions that operate as though the world is without limits then it will have failed before it begins. And if this symposium fails to state that the basis of all environmental deterioration is simply that there are too many people or, in any way, it aligns itself with policies that see Australia divorced from its global setting then it will have proved itself morally culpable.

Biology can and must provide a basis for an objective assessment of man as a species, but unless we seek for an immediate re-examination of the basic philosophies around which the institutions we foster and represent are built then we will have failed in our duty as scientists and we will have hastened the collapse of the biosphere.

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